

The Experiment for Characterizing the Lower Ionosphere and Prediction Sporadic-E (ECLIPSE) Missions: Instruments to Study the Dynamics of the Lower Ionosphere

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Abstract

The Naval Research Laboratory designed and developed small instruments for flight on CubeSats to study the Earth's ionosphere. These instruments have been incorporated into an experiment called the Experiment for Characterizing the Lower Ionosphere and Production of Sporadic-E (ECLIPSE). One instrument is a photometer, called the Triple-Tiny Ionospheric Photometer (Tri-TIP), used to measure the brightness of the O I 135.6 nm emission, which during nighttime is produced primarily by radiative recombination of O⁺ ions and electrons. At nighttime this emission can be used to infer the distribution of electrons in the ionosphere. A second instrument, called the Triple-Magnesium Ion Photometer (Tri-MIP), is designed to measure the Mg II 280 nm emission, which is produced during the daytime by scattering of sunlight by Mg⁺ ions in the ionosphere. Mg⁺ ions are produced by meteoric ablation and also by charge exchange between molecular ions and Mg atoms produced during the meteor ablation. Mg⁺ ions act as tracers of the dynamical drivers in the E- and F-regions of the ionosphere. Prior measurements of both species have been used to determine the two-dimensional distribution of the ions in the orbit plane of the satellite making the measurements. In this paper, we describe the experiments and some observations of the Tri-TIP and Tri-MIP instruments on the two missions.

Introduction

The Experiment for Characterizing the Lower Ionosphere and Prediction Sporadic-E (ECLIPSE) instruments are compact, highly-sensitive sensors built by the U.S. Naval Research Laboratory as technology demonstrations for observing the bottom-side of Earth's ionosphere to characterize plasma density structures and for observing the spatial distribution of metallic ions generated by meteor ablation. The overall science objective of the missions is: *To observe the small- to medium-scale 3D structure of the bottom-side ionosphere to study the dynamical drivers that generate the spatial variations and to elucidate how the structures and the drivers vary globally.* The approach we have adopted is to extend prior work by the NRL to study smaller scale structures in the bottom-side ionosphere. Our approach is broken down into four scientific tasks: 1) Use Multi-Perspective Ultraviolet (MPUV) measurements to provide higher spatial resolution imaging of the ionospheric structures than can be obtained using standard measurement techniques. 2) The MPUV measurements are interpreted using two- and three-dimensional tomographic reconstruction techniques using accurate emission physics. 3) Assimilative modeling of the ionosphere and thermosphere will be used to provide prior estimates of the species densities, which is sometimes necessary for tomography; to provide background ionospheric specification

as context for the observations; and also to ingest the species densities generated from the tomographic inversions to produce higher fidelity regional ionospheric specification. 4) Lastly, the measurements and ionospheric specifications will be validated using alternative measurements, such as ground-based digisondes or incoherent scatter radars.

The development and evolution of small- to medium-scale 3D spatial structures in the bottomside ionosphere is an active area of research, yet the global occurrence rates of these spatial structures is not well understood. The principal instruments for studying the bottomside ionosphere are ground-based radars, such as incoherent scatter radars or bottomside sounders. While these devices are extraordinarily sensitive to the bottomside structure, they are large and there are only a few of them, which limits their geographical coverage. Another data source that has been used to characterize the 3D ionospheric structure is ground based GPS receivers, which are predominantly land-based. Thus the data sources leave the open oceans under-sampled. Because the types and prevalence of the various dynamical drivers (for example medium-scale traveling ionospheric disturbances, mountain waves, ionospheric bubbles and depletions) varies both globally and regionally, the limited geographic coverage of the radars and GPS receivers means that the drivers and the types of the small- to medium-scale 3D structures have been studied in very limited geographic regions. Space-based sensing is required to provide the global view needed to understand the types of structures present at different locations on the Earth and how they impact radio-frequency propagation. However, it is not possible to observe these structures using state-of-the-art space-based sensors because they lack the sensitivity and/or the spatial resolution and their orbital altitudes are too high to adequately observe the bottomside ionosphere. Next-generation space-based MPOV sensors, improved tomographic imaging techniques, and assimilative models should enable the imaging of small- to medium-scale 3D ionospheric structures in the bottomside ionosphere beneath the satellite's orbit.

Small- to Medium-Scale Structures in the Ionosphere

Figure 1 shows a simulation of Medium Scale Travelling Ionospheric Disturbances (MSTIDs) that were generated by gravity waves created by intense thunderstorms in Texas on April 4, 2014 at 8:00-10:30 UTC [Azeem *et al.*, 2015, 2020]. These concentric waves propagated over all of North America. Zawdie *et al.* [2018a, 2018b, and 2019] modeled these waves, as is shown in Figure 1, using the SAMI3 model [Huba, Joyce, and Fedder 2000; Huba and Liu, 2020] nudged by a simulated gravity wave propagated up from the thermosphere. Figure 1a, shows the time rate of change of the temperature in the lower thermosphere (at 100 km) driven by the simulated gravity waves driven by the thunderstorm. Figure 1b shows the electron density modeled using the SAMI3 model nudged by the gravity wave. The gravity wave from panel (a) is rotated and shown beneath the electron density. Note that there are slight perturbations to the electron density at 300 km (top of the cube) as indicated by the slight pink colorations. If we rotate this electron density cube backward to view the bottom-side, we get the view shown in Figure 1c. The MSTIDs are obvious. Can we build space-based instruments with the sensitivity and spatial resolution to characterize this type of phenomenon? The ECLIPSE instruments should be capable of making observations to provide characterization of these types of phenomena at nighttime.

Figure 2 shows observations made by the Ionospheric Chemistry And Atmospheric Chemistry (ISAAC) instrument which flew on the United States Air Force Space Test Program Advanced Research and Global Observing Satellite (ARGOS) from 1999-2002 [Wolfram *et al.*, 1999]. The ISAAC instrument was a spectrographic imager with a field-of-view (FOV) that was scanned

Figure 1: Simulation of MSTID over Texas. Panel (a) shows the temporal variation of the thermospheric temperature at 100 km altitude over the thunderstorm activity. Panel (b) shows the electron density in the ionosphere over the thunderstorm; note that the common logarithm of the density is displayed. Panel (c) shows the bottom-side view of the electron density in panel (b) showing the presence of the MSTID perturbations on the density.

Figure 2: Mg⁺ Patchiness and Layering: Panel (a) shows spectra gathered in a “stare mode” where the instrument was staring at ~100 km altitude. The spectral intensity is color encoded using the same color bar as in Figure 2b, but covering ~0-10 kilo-Rayleighs. Note that there are emissions present from both Fe⁺ (although the Fe⁺ emission is difficult to see in this image) and Mg⁺, and that these emissions are patchy in nature. Figure 2b shows the Mg⁺ density derived by tomographic inversion of the limb scan observations made by the ISAAC instrument during an orbit that passed over the equator at 112° E on June 2000. The vertical dashed lines indicate the geomagnetic coordinates, -60°, -30°, 0°, 30°, and 60°. Note that there are patches and layers present and enhanced densities near the geomagnetic equator.

Figure 3: MPUV Measurements. Panel (a) shows the VER for the O I 135.6 nm emission at night based on a simulation using the SAMI-3 model output [Huba, Joyce, and Fedder 2000; Huba and Liu, 2020]. Panel (b) shows the ECLIPSE observations concept. The orange bar on the left side of the image indicates the instantaneous FOV of one of the ALS instruments with the purple pyramidal shape indicating the FOR of the ALS instrument. The FOV is scanned vertically across the FOR as indicated by the two-headed yellow arrow. The red curves on the globe indicate the FOR of one of the Cross-track Scanner Instruments. Its FOV is indicated by the white bar near the two-headed yellow arrow. Panel (c) shows the intersecting lines-of-sight from the instruments overlapped on the SAMI3 output .

vertically above the horizon using a scanning assembly. Figure 2a shows spectra gathered in a “stare mode” where the ISAAC instrument was staring at an altitude of ~100 km. The spectral intensity is color encoded using the same color bar as in Figure 2b, but covering ~0-10 kilo-Rayleighs. The blue to green spectra near 800-2000 seconds and again after 5000 seconds is the dayglow spectrum showing mostly emission from molecular nitrogen in the Vegard-Kaplan bands [Wolfram *et al.*, 1999]. The blank region of the Panel (a) between times of ~2500-5000 s, is the nighttime section of the orbit. Note that there are emissions present from both Fe⁺ (although the Fe⁺ emission is difficult to see in this image) and Mg⁺, and that these emissions are patchy in nature. This patchiness is generally caused by wind-shear driven by atmospheric tides causing a pile-up of the ions. Figure 2b shows the Mg⁺ density derived by tomographic inversion of the limb scan observations made by the ISAAC instrument during June 2000. The vertical dashed lines indicate the geomagnetic coordinates, -60°, -30°, 0°, 30°, and 60°. Note that there are patches and

layers present in the results. In addition, there are enhanced densities near the geomagnetic equator, which are caused by $\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ drift which lifts the plasma in the region near the geomagnetic equator. These characteristics have been observed by the ECLIPSE-RR mission, as discussed below.

Multi-Perspective UltraViolet (MPUV) Measurements

MPUV measurements are observations of the same volume of space made from multiple viewing perspectives. ECLIPSE is an example of an MPUV instrument [Dymond *et al.*, 2023]. This experiment was installed on the *International Space Station* on March 17, 2023 and is gathering data. The ECLIPSE ISS mission uses a cross-track scanning photometer to make high sensitivity and spatial resolution images of the emissions beneath the ISS as shown in Figure 3. This mission also uses limb-scanning photometers that view aft of the ISS to measure the altitude distribution of the emissions. During the daytime, the combination of these two viewing directions should permit the determination of the 3D distribution of Mg^+ ions near the orbit plane of the ISS. At night, a similar pair of instruments will measure the 135.6 nm emission produced primarily by the recombination of O^+ ions and electrons at night, which should permit the determination of the 3D distribution of electrons near the orbit plane of the ISS. In Figure 3, panel (a) shows the optically thick Volume Emission Rate (VER, photons emitted per second per unit volume) for the O I 135.6 nm emission at night based on a simulation using the SAMI-3 model output [Zawdie *et al.*, 2018a, 2018b, and 2019]. The enhancement near 100-150 km at 10-30° N is caused by photons created by recombination at higher altitudes (250-400 km in this image) that have been entrapped by multiple resonant scattering by atomic oxygen atoms in the lower thermosphere. Panel (b) shows a cartoon of the ECLIPSE observations concept. The orange bar on the left side of the image indicates the instantaneous field-of-view (FOV) of one of the Aft Limb Scanner (ALS) instruments with the pyramidal shape indicating the field-of-regard (FOR) of the ALS instrument. The FOV is scanned vertically across the FOR with altitude coverage of ~50-400 km. The red curves beneath the ISS picture indicate the FOR of one of the Cross-track Scanner Instruments. Its FOV is indicated by the white bar near the two-headed yellow arrow. The FOR covers approximately ± 400 km on either side of the ISS orbit plane and the FOV is scanned back and forth across the FOR. Panel (c) shows the intersection of the lines-of-sight from the limb scanning instrument, which are curved in this image because the Earth's curvature has been removed, and the in-plane vertical lines of sight, indicated by the vertical lines. The intersecting lines-of-sight from the instrument shows the multi-perspective nature of the observations and enables tomographic interpretation of the measurements to reconstruct the 2D photon emission rate distribution, which is then back-solved to infer the species density distribution.

The ECLIPSE-RR instrument on the Slingshot-1 CubeSat mission, discussed below, scans viewing aft of the CubeSat, like the ECLIPSE ALS. ECLIPSE-RR is an MPUV instrument that was launched into orbit on July 2, 2022 and is gathering data on the Mg^+ ion distribution. This instrument performs limb scans aft of the Slingshot-1 satellite and has measured the 2D distribution of Mg^+ ions near the orbit plane of the CubeSat.

Another example of a MPUV instrument is the Special Sensor Ultraviolet Limb Imager that flew on the DMSP satellites [Dymond *et al.*, 2017a]. The SSULI instruments and their precursor, the Low-resolution Airglow and Aurora Spectrograph (LORAAS) instrument that flew on the STP Advanced Research and Global Observing Satellite (ARGOS) from 1999-2002, demonstrated ionospheric tomography using UV measurements [Dymond and Thomas, 2001; Dymond *et al.*, 2017b, c]. The LORAAS instrument flew with the ISAAC instrument that was used to demonstrate tomographic imagery of the Mg^+ ions [Wolfram *et al.*, 1999].

Figure 4: A diagram of the Slingshot-1 satellite is shown on the left with the Tri-MIP/SUVM indicated by the green oval. The NRL Tri-MIP/SUVM combination is shown on the right. Each unit of the Tri-MIP/SUVM is one “U” in size (10 cm × 10 cm × 10 cm) with a mass of ~ 1 kg.

ECLIPSE-Risk Reduction Observations

A prototype of the Tri-MIP instrument was built and launched as the ECLIPSE-Risk Reduction (ECLIPSE-RR) payload on a recent CubeSat mission into low Earth orbit to study the spatial distribution of Mg^+ ions. The satellite (Slingshot-1), a collaboration with the Aerospace Corporation, was launched via the DoD Space Test Program (STP) out of Southern California on the Virgin Orbit launch that occurred on July 2, 2022. The orbit is near circular at an altitude of 555 km and an inclination angle of 45° . Figure 4 shows a picture of the Slingshot-1 satellite and the ECLIPSE-RR instrument, which consists of a Triple-Magnesium Ion Photometer (Tri-MIP) with a Scanning Ultraviolet Mirror (SUVM). The Tri-MIP is a photometer containing three photomultiplier tubes (PMTs) to measure the intensities of the Mg II 280 nm line, a background band at 277 nm, and the dark count which characterizes the high energy particle background. Each Tri-MIP features two co-aligned photometers that use Fresnel lenses to image the airglow and optical filters to limit the passbands. The FOV of the instruments are scanned across the FOR using the SUVM. The photometers, Sun protection shutters, and the high voltage power supplies for the instrument are contained in a 1U structure with command and control electronics to interface with a CubeSat. The SUVM with its scan mirror, mirror drive motor, and control electronics is also contained within a 1U assembly. The Tri-MIP instruments are described in detail in *Nicholas et al.* [2021]. Data acquisition began in September 2022 with disk scans, in which the FOV is held at a fixed angle viewing downward onto the Earth’s disk. Due to an undiagnosed issue with the CubeSat flight software, the telemetry from the SUVM is not transmitted to ground. On orbit testing of the SUVM scan mirror indicate that it is working correctly, but without the mirror pointing information, it is difficult to interpret the results. To perform the disk scan, we have opted to position the scan mirror near the center of its scan range. This results in the Tri-MIP FOV being oriented downward 45° below the satellite’s horizon. Limb scans have been performed using the attitude control system on the SLINGSHOT satellite. This has resulted in non-optimal scan rates for tomographic imaging, but the results have been adequate to demonstrate the instrument and tomographic imaging. The limb scan tomography started on November 22 and continued through

Figure 5: Tomography results for December 25, 2022 at 10.69 and 14.03 UT. Panels (a) and (c) show the Slingshot orbits (white lines) with locations of the reconstruction grid shown as red dots. The light blue lines indicate the magnetic equator and $\pm 20^\circ$ magnetic latitudes. The sub-solar point is indicated by the yellow circles. The data gathers begin near the Southwestern edges of the images and proceed Northeasterly. Panels (b) and (d) show the tomographic reconstructions of the Mg^+ density as functions of altitude and orbit phase angle (degrees). The light blue vertical lines indicate where the orbit crosses the geomagnetic latitudes: 0° , $\pm 10^\circ$, and $\pm 20^\circ$.

the February 22. Disk scans were run from February 23-April 27. Limb scanning resumed on April 27 and is continuing as of June 2023.

ECLIPSE-RR 2D Tomography Results: Figure 5 shows the Tomography results for observations made on December 25, 2022 at 10.69 and 14.03 UT. Panels (a) and (c) show the Slingshot-1 orbits (white lines) with locations of the reconstruction grid shown as red dots. The light blue lines indicate the magnetic equator and $\pm 20^\circ$ magnetic latitudes. The sub-solar point is indicated by the yellow circles. The data gathers begin near Southwestern edges of the images and proceed Northeasterly. Panels (b) and (d) show the tomographic reconstructions of the Mg^+ density as functions of altitude and orbit phase angle (degrees) using the Least Squares Positive Definite (LSPD) algorithm [Dymond *et al.*, 2017b]. The Mg II 280 nm radiance is calculated by scaling the background band radiance in the 277 nm band to remove signal contamination by emission from the N_2 Vegard-Kaplan bands and at lower altitudes by Rayleigh scattered sunlight. The radiances are also corrected for the “dark” background, which is due to on-orbit counts caused by high energy particle excitation of the photomultiplier tubes. The radiances are then inverted using a

Figure 6: Disk scan data for February 27, 2023 between 03:12:59 and 07:17:09 UT. Panel (a) shows the Slingshot orbits with the observed Mg^+ radiance color encoded. The light blue lines indicate the magnetic equator and $\pm 20^\circ$ magnetic latitudes. The sub-solar point is indicated by the yellow ovoid, which starts at $\sim 135^\circ$ E longitude and traverses westward to $\sim 70^\circ$ E. The data gather starts near Southern Africa indicated by the blue asterisk. Nighttime measurements are shown in black, as no counts were observed by the Tri-MIP. Panel (b) shows the Mg^+ radiances versus UT. There is some “patchiness” observed as the fine-scale structure.

tomographic inversion scheme based on the LSPD algorithm and converted to the volume emission rate of the Mg II 280 nm emission ($\text{photons s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-3}$), which is converted to the number density by dividing by the resonance fluorescence efficiency or g-factor (photons s^{-1}) due to solar fluorescence excitation of the Mg^+ emission (see *Dymond et al.* [2003] for the evaluation of the g-factor). The light blue vertical lines indicate where the orbit crosses the geomagnetic latitudes: 0° , $\pm 10^\circ$, and $\pm 20^\circ$. Note that in panel (b) the Mg^+ density tends to peak near 0° N magnetic latitude, while it peaks at $\sim 17^\circ$ N in panel (d). Similar vertical enhancements were noted in the ISAAC tomographic reconstructions, as shown in Figure 2b. Mg^+ is also exhibiting layering near 120 km altitudes in both of these images, again layering at these altitudes has been previously noted in the ISAAC tomography results in Figure 2b. Recent modeling of the Mg^+ density distribution using the SAMI-3 model driven by NRLMSIS [*Picone et al.*, 2002] and the HWM [*Drob et al.*, 2015] model also showed layering at ~ 100 -120 km altitudes. The high density regions near the left and right edges of the panels 5(b) and 5(d) are reconstruction artifacts and are not true density enhancements.

ECLIPSE-RR 2D Disk Scan Results: Figure 6 shows disk scan data for February 27, 2023 between 03:12:59 and 07:17:09 UT. The data were processed to convert the measured count rates into radiances, but tomographic inversions were not performed on this data set because of the lack of intersecting lines-of-sight. The lines-of-sight for these measurements were oriented 45° below the local horizon of the vehicle with resulted in the lines-of-sight intersecting the 100 km altitude level at 455 km behind the satellite, which was at an altitude of ~ 555 km. Panel (a) shows the Slingshot-1 orbits with the observed Mg^+ radiance color encoded. The light blue lines indicate the magnetic equator and $\pm 20^\circ$ magnetic latitudes. The sub-solar point is indicated by the yellow ovoid, which starts at $\sim 135^\circ$ E longitude and traverses westward to $\sim 70^\circ$ E. The data gather starts near Southern Africa indicated by the blue asterisk. Nighttime measurements are shown in black, as no counts were observed by the Tri-MIP. Panel (b) shows the Mg^+ radiances versus UT. There is some

Figure 7: The ECLIPSE flight hardware is shown prior to its delivery to NASA’s Johnson Space Center in March 2022. (a) Cross-track Scanner (CTS), which views beneath the ISS and produces maps of the airglow emission. (b) Aft Limb-Scanner (ALS), which makes images of the ionospheric airglow behind the ISS in its orbit plane. (c) Mission Operations Electronics (MOE), which commands and controls the ECLIPSE experiment during the mission.

“patchiness” observed as the fine-scale structure. The enhancements present on the first two orbits near 4.3 and 5.9 UT are not understood at this time. They are not present in most of the disk scan data. The Mg^+ “patchiness” is evidenced by the rapid fine scale fluctuations in the signal between 3.5 and 4.1 UT, 5.1 and 5.7 UT, and 6.7 and 7.3 UT.

Additional analysis of the ECLIPSE-RR data is ongoing. We are in the process of routinely processing the tomography and disk scan data and are beginning to perform comparisons against ground truth data sets. Additional ECLIPSE-RR results can be found in: *Fritz et al.* [2023]. We also hope to gather coincident observations with the ECLIPSE ISS mission.

ECLIPSE ISS Mission

The second mission, ECLIPSE, is flying two Tri-MIPs and two Tri-TIPs on the United Space Force Space Test Program’s STP-H9 mission that was installed on the International Space Station on March 17, 2023. The ECLIPSE mission features one Tri-TIP and one Tri-MIP with scanning mirrors that scan the Earth’s limb behind the ISS to make limb scans versus altitude in the orbit plane of the ISS. The mission also includes one Tri-TIP and one Tri-MIP viewing downward beneath the ISS and scanning cross-track to make 2D observations over the globe. In this paper, we also present early mission results showing both the horizontal structures and the distribution of Mg^+ ions in the satellite’s orbit plane and make comparisons to a coupled ionosphere/thermosphere model.

ECLIPSE Hardware: Figure 7 shows a picture of the ECLIPSE flight hardware prior to its delivery to NASA’s Johnson Space Center in March 2022. The box on the upper left in the image (a) is the Cross-track Scanner (CTS), which views beneath the ISS and produces maps of the airglow emission. The sensor on the upper right (b) is the Aft Limb-Scanner (ALS), which makes images of the ionospheric airglow behind the ISS in its orbit plane. Each scanner contains one Tri-

TIP/SUVM and one Tri-MIP/SUVM assembly. The blackened rectangular structures on the boxes are the sunshade baffles around the openings to the SUVM mirrors, which are at the center of the baffles. The box near the bottom center (c) is the Mission Operations Electronics (MOE), which controls the instruments and accepts commands from the ISS and relays data back to the ISS during the mission. In addition to two Tri-MIP/SUVM combinations, ECLIPSE also contains two Triple-Tiny Ionospheric Photometers (Tri-TIPs) [Dymond *et al.*, 2017d] with SUVMs. The Tri-TIP is a photometer, which is an evolved version of the Tiny Ionospheric Photometers (TIP) flown on the Constellation Observing System for Meteorology, Ionosphere, and Climate (COSMIC) [COSMIC: Anthes *et al.*, 2008; TIP: Dymond *et al.*, 2016; Dymond, Nee, and Thomas, 2000; Budzien *et al.*, 2009]. The Tri-TIPs contain three photomultiplier tubes (PMTs) to measure the intensities of the O I 135.6 nm line, a background band that observes wavelengths longer than 137 nm, and the dark count which characterizes the high energy particle background. Each Tri-TIP features two co-aligned photometers that share a common off-axis parabolic telescope to image the airglow and optical filters to limit the passbands. Under normal flight observations, the Tri-MIP/SUVMs will be used on the dayside to observe the Mg⁺ emission, while the Tri-TIP/SUVMs will be operated at night to observe the O I 135.6 nm emission.

Figure 8 shows pictures of the ECLIPSE ISS mission. The logos of the DoD Space Test Program STP-H9 and the ECLIPSE experiment are shown in the figure. The STP-H9 launch from Cape Canaveral, FL on March 15, 2023 is shown in the third picture in the top row. The last picture shows the STP-H9 carrier pre-launch launch. The VVIPRE (a copy of the SSULI [Dymond *et al.*, 2017a]), ECLIPSE (ALS only, the CTS is on the bottom of the carrier and is not visible), and SOHIP [McGuffin *et al.*, 2023; Wampler, 2023] instruments are indicated. The first picture in the bottom row shows the STP-H9 carrier inside the Space-X trunk on the ISS. The middle picture on the bottom row shows the STP-H9 carrier being installed onto the ISS by the robotic arm. The picture on the right in the bottom row shows the STP-H9 carrier installed in its position on the ISS with the Earth in the background.

The ECLIPSE mission instruments are still in the commissioning state at the time of this writing (June 2023) and data are not available. Instead we show the results of data simulations using ionospheric model output. The ECLIPSE CTS FOR covers $\pm 45^\circ$ on either side of the ISS orbit plane, this corresponds to a cross-track coverage of ~ 400 km on either side of the orbit plane. The spatial resolution is ~ 30 km (along-track) by 30 km cross-track. The ECLIPSE ALS scans aft of the ISS and the scan range will need to be adjusted to avoid glint and obstructions due to other payloads or the solar arrays on the ISS. The nominal scan range is from the local horizon aft (~ 400 km altitude) of the ISS downward to ~ 50 km. The altitude resolution is ~ 5 km. Other operational modes have the scan down onto the disk. Figure 9 shows the simulated radiance for the Mg⁺ 280 nm emission during a daytime pass. Panel (a) shows the aft limb scan radiance for scans covering the 70-360 km altitude range. Note the layer near 100 km altitudes at latitudes between 20-30° N. This layer shows up in as a bright “hourglass” shaped enhancement near the center of Panel (b), which shows the cross-track scanning radiance simulation. The black line across the image is the ISS orbit. The ISS path is from southwest to northeast in this simulation. When the ISS is at an altitude of ~ 400 km, the width of the cross-track swath is approximately 800 km, when the SUVM is scanned through its full range. Figure 9 shows the simulated radiance of the nighttime O I 135.6 nm emission. Panel (a) shows the limb scan radiance; note that some bottomside radiance, at $z < 200$ km, near is seen orbit phase angles $< 10^\circ$. Panel (b) shows the simulated cross-track radiance.

Figure 8: ECLIPSE on the ISS: Upper left shows the logos of the DoD Space Test Program STP-H9 and the ECLIPSE experiment. The STP-H9 launch from Cape Canaveral, FL on March 15, 2023 is shown in the third picture in the top row. The last picture shows a picture of the STP-H9 carrier prior to integrating into the launcher. The VVIPRE, ECLIPSE (ALS, the CTS is on the bottom of the carrier), and SOHIP instruments are indicated. The first picture in the bottom row shows the STP-H9 carrier inside the Space-X trunk on the ISS. The middle picture on the bottom row shows the STP-H9 carrier being installed onto the ISS by the robotic arm. The picture on the right in the bottom row shows the STP-H9 carrier installed in its position on the ISS with the Earth in the background.

Showing Closure

We have several criteria that we plan to execute to show that we have met our science objective. Table 1 contains a summary of our goals, approach, and rationale. 1) We plan to extensively validate our measurements against ground truth in regions where there is a high density of ionospheric measurements, such as over North America and Europe. This will allow us to learn what structures are visible to our measurements and methodology. 2) We plan to characterize the types of structures present in our imagery. Characteristics of interest include: wave fronts, density enhancements, normal directions to linear enhancements, and presence of density depletions. This will help us determine what we can observe and help us to classify the possible dynamical drivers of the structures. 3) Characterize the global and temporal occurrence rates for the structures. This would permit us to extend the observations of structure in regions of high measurement density to other areas and regions and provide additional clues to the dynamical drivers. 4) Lastly, flight aboard the ISS provides a unique opportunity to compare our measurements to coincident measurements made by other instruments aboard the ISS, for example the SOHIP [McGuffin *et al.*, 2023; Wampler, 2023] instrument mentioned earlier. This instrument is designed to measure the presence of gravity waves propagating vertically in the troposphere and stratosphere. This provides a unique opportunity to search for gravity wave perturbations in the ionosphere occurring simultaneously with gravity waves observed in the lower atmosphere. The NASA Atmospheric Waves Experiment (AWE: Taylor *et al.* [2020]) is also slated to launch while ECLIPSE is operating. The AWE experiment is designed to observe gravity waves at nighttime beneath the ISS with the same cross-track coverage as ECLIPSE. This presents another unique opportunity to study gravity wave coupling from the lower atmosphere into the ionosphere.

Figure 9: Daytime Mg^+ Radiance: Panel (a) shows the aft limb scan radiance. Panel (b) shows the cross-track radiance. The black line across the image is the ISS orbit. The ISS path is from southwest to northeast in this simulation.

Figure 10: The nighttime O I 135.6 nm emission radiance is shown. Panel (a) shows the limb scan radiance, while panel (b) shows the cross-track nadir radiance assuming the ISS is at an altitude of ~400 km. The black line across the nadir radiance indicates the ISS orbit plane. The width of the cross-track swath is approximately 800 km.

Approach	Rationale
Validate our 3D specifications in regions with high ground-truth measurement density, e.g. the USA and Europe.	Learn what structures are visible and verify that they are visible using other methods too: this will permit possible identification of the structures and their drivers.
Characterize the structures present in our 3D imagery: look for characteristic wavelengths, normal directions to wave fronts, ionospheric depletions, etc.	Determine what can be observed and use observed characteristics to identify the types of structures and infer their dynamical drivers.
Characterize global and temporal occurrence rates for structures.	Determine how the various structures vary on a global basis and in time: another clue to the possible dynamical drivers.
Use coincident measurements of gravity waves and other drivers from on-board the ISS to aid in the interpretation of the observed structures.	Provide a direct correspondence between the observed ionospheric structure and the dynamical drivers.

Table 1: Requirements for Closure: The approaches we plan to adopt to demonstrate closure of the science mission goal are listed.

Summary

We provided a brief overview of the ECLIPSE Missions. We briefly described the hardware and the types of observations that can be made. We discussed the science topics that we are planning to address and, in the case of the ECLIPSE-RR mission, are already addressing. We presented some results from the ECLIPSE-RR mission and have found reasonable agreement with the SAMI-3 model driven by the HWM and NRLMSIS models. The models predicted layering in the lower ionosphere and also some patchiness, both of which were observed by the ECLIPSE-RR instrument. We show both disk scan results and 2D in-plane tomography results from ECLIPSE-RR. For the ECLIPSE mission, we presented some simulations that illustrate the expected measurement capability of the mission. We also discussed our principal science objective and the planned approaches to show closure.

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